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Abstract: The increasing availability of chemical probes for specific applications in chemical biology and medicinal chemistry is extensively facilitating our knowledge of biological systems. This understanding has fundamental implications in the development of new efficacious therapeutic strategies. Nowadays, successful drug discovery programs consider identification, engagement, and endogenous levels of the intended therapeutic target from the earliest preclinical stages. All these aspects are addressed with the use of chemical probes, compounds that rely on the use of a particular chemical reaction to give an answer to a specific biological question. In this review we will describe the underlying chemistry and the most recent advances experienced by the field together with their most important biomedical applications.

1. Introduction

Identification of new therapeutic targets remains a critical need in the field of current drug development. Recent target annotations indicate that the existing drugs in the market only target less than 700 human proteins.^[1] Taking into account that some analyses estimate that only 11% of the potential targets in the proteome have ligands,^[2] the situation is that current drugs target less than one-tenth of the available human proteome. This fact is due to a significant lack of understanding of human biology, which is hampering the advance of new treatment strategies. Developing more robust therapeutic hypotheses requires a deeper comprehension of all disease-relevant genes and the functional annotation of its cognate proteins. The importance of this objective has been recently recognized by the scientific community with the Target 2035 Challenge, aimed at the identification of a small-molecule or antibody probe for every protein in the human proteome by 2035.^[3] As we are conscious about the vast space that could be exploited for increasing efficacy, safety, and capacity to face the many unmet clinical needs, we also recognize the enormous potential of organic chemistry, with its capacity for creating tailored small molecules with the sought and iteratively optimized properties, to help in such an endeavor. The scope of this review will be focused on small molecules (referred to as probes or chemical probes) that although not necessarily comply with all the features to be suitable for their use as drugs can be used *in vitro* or *in vivo* to confirm biological hypotheses with medical relevance. Although other macromolecules such as nucleic acids can be also therapeutic targets, in this review we will limit our attention to proteins, taking into account that they represent the majority of the therapeutic targets under exploitation by current marketed drugs and that other excellent reviews have recently covered the nucleic acid field.^[4]

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Beatriz Marcos-Ramiro's research career has been devoted to gain insights on the mechanisms underlying different pathological conditions in the quest for effective treatments. In this context, she has studied inflammation under physiological and pathological conditions. She has made important contributions to the understanding of pathophysiology of multiple sclerosis, to the formation and development of medulloblastomas, a type of pediatric brain tumor, and to the validation of the enzyme isoprenylcysteine carboxylmethyltransferase (ICMT) inhibitors for the treatment of Ras-dependent cancers and progeria.

Silvia Ortega-Gutiérrez is associate professor in the Medicinal Chemistry Laboratory at Complutense University. Her research interests focus on the development of new pharmacological strategies for treating diseases that currently lack efficacious therapies using chemical biology and medicinal chemistry approaches. In this regard, she works on the validation of new therapeutic targets for neuropathic pain, cancer or progeria as well as on the identification of novel protein targets using chemical probes.

Identification of a protein, ideally with importance for a given disease, usually requires two main aspects: visualization and capture in the most relevant and native biological conditions. Along this review, both concepts, visualization and identification, will be thoroughly discussed. By identification we mean the unequivocal assignation of the identity of a protein. This usually requires the use of covalent probes that enable protein isolation and mass spectrometry based sequencing and identification.^[5] For visualization, however, irreversible binding is not mandatory, as long as enough affinity between the probe and protein exists and typical visualization experiments can be performed. These

include, for example, confocal microscopy or flow cytometry to assess the cellular localization or the expression levels of a protein of interest. Hence, chemical probes, in their most basic structure, must contain three elements: (i) a moiety with affinity for the protein of interest; (ii) a reporter subunit, that can be a fluorophore (or other fragment suitable for visualization using different techniques), or an affinity tag for subsequent capture, such as biotin (although there are others); and (iii) a linker that connects these two moieties. In some occasions, a small group (for example a terminal alkyne, an azide, a phosphine group, or cyclopropene or tetrazine rings) suitable for bioorthogonal reactions can be a surrogate of the reporter, so that the required fluorescent or affinity tags, usually bigger sized, can be incorporated in a later stage. Finally, a linker usually separates the two elements, the biologically active moiety and the reporter subunit. Optimization of this linker is of critical importance, as it can impact important properties such as solubility or membrane penetration. In addition, the inclusion of a moiety suitable for covalent or irreversible binding to the protein of interest is an important aspect when considering the degree of reversibility required for the intended use of the probe. Although some authors restrict the use of the term “chemical probes” to small molecules with proven affinity, specificity, and selectivity (ie, as a synonym of ligands or pharmacological regulator of exceptional quality in terms of potency, affinity, and/or selectivity and specificity),^[3] throughout this manuscript we will refer to probes as small molecules which, besides showing affinity, specificity, and selectivity, contain in their structure a reporter subunit (or a surrogate such as a bioorthogonal group suitable for the introduction of the reporter in an upcoming step) able to shed light on protein visualization or identification aspects (see Figure 1 for a schematic representation). This type of probes have also been expressed as “linkered probes”, to differentiate from the term “probes” (or “linker-free probes”) with the above-mentioned meaning.^[2]

In this review we will describe the most recent advances in the development of chemical probes and their validated biomedical applications organized by the underlying chemistry and the therapeutic targets involved.

Figure 1. Schematic representation of a chemical probe.

2. Binding and reporter groups: the matter of (ir)reversibility and the size importance

As mentioned in the previous section, there are three main parts in the structure of a probe: (a) the binding group, with affinity for or functional activity at the protein of interest; (b) the reporter group, which will impart the desired property of visualization or capture ability; and (c) the linker that joins these two parts.

2.1. The binding group

The binding group is the part of the molecule responsible for the specific and efficacious recognition of the protein of interest

among all the molecules present in the highly complex biological media. Its main features are the degree of affinity for the protein, its activity potency (if applicable), its mechanism of action in terms of binding reversibility, and the possibilities for structural modifications so that the initial ligand can be transformed into a probe with the introduction of the reporter. The binding group usually comes from a previously described ligand of the protein of interest that has been slightly modified to incorporate the other elements of the probe (ie the linker and the reporter group). With respect to the degree of affinity, in principle an affinity as high as possible is desired, taking into account that, in general, lower probe concentration will potentially involve less problems of promiscuity and will increase probe specificity. In this regard, nanomolar affinity is usually sought. However, while this value can be attainable in enzyme and G protein-coupled receptor (GPCR) ligands, it is quite challenging in other targets such as those involved in protein-protein or protein-nucleic acid interactions or in those targets with poor structural characterization. In these cases, single digit micromolar affinities can be admitted as starting points. In general, to qualify as a high-quality binding group, the initial ligand should have biochemical potency better than 100 nM (IC_{50} or K_D), high selectivity (more than 30-fold within the targeted protein family and 100-fold against other non-related targets), and potent cellular activity (EC_{50} values better than 1 μ M in cellular assays). Obviously, starting with ligands with properties as close as possible to the mentioned ones increases the possibility of success in the quality of the final resulting probe, as the introduction of the other subunits (linker and reporter) usually involves decreases in affinity and/or activity, as the initial ligands tend to be optimized for their respective targets.

Regarding the mechanism of action, probes can bind in a reversible or in an irreversible manner. Usually, a reversible probe binds by a number of non-covalent interactions so that the total energy binding is favorable in thermodynamic terms. However, it is an equilibrium driven by the corresponding binding constant. The lower the dissociation constant, the stronger the interaction between the ligand and the protein. However, the kinetic of the binding is a feature that also has to be considered, because there are rapid binders (which are quickly detached from their target proteins) and slow binders, which remain bound for longer periods of time and can behave, in extreme cases, similarly to irreversible binders. Regardless of the kinetic aspect, any reversible reaction will be in equilibrium between the bound and unbound state, so reversible probes will be well suited for some applications but they will not be so appropriate for other purposes that require permanent and strong binding between the probe and the protein. Conversely, an irreversible probe is chemistry driven and the chemical reaction dictates the specificity and the reaction rate. A covalent probe tends to bind irreversibly to its targets, although in some cases there is some reversibility that appears with time. Usually, covalent probes are faster binders than their non-covalent counterparts and they establish long-durable interactions between the probe and its ligand, thus making possible other applications for which non-covalent probes are not suitable. These aspects will be discussed in more detail in the following sections.

2.2. The reporter group

In the field of therapeutic target validation, probes are used to obtain mainly two types of information: visualization and identification. Accordingly, the reporter groups can be classified

into two broad classes based on these two applications. In this section we will summarize the most important reporter groups for both applications:

a) Visualization reporter groups: Monitoring and visualizing essential cell processes are critical activities for drug development. Target visualization is of crucial importance to confirm the expression at the cellular or histological level (target distribution) and to assess target engagement. Determining target expression level in native and physiological conditions is important to ensure that the intended drug target is expressed in the tissue of interest and not (or at least with lower levels of expression) in other tissues where it could cause undesired side toxic effects. Also, probes to assess whether a drug effectively binds the expected protein *in vivo* (ie *in vivo* target engagement) represent one of the most valuable agents for the true advance of drug candidates during the drug discovery process. Establishing the subcellular localization may be also useful in drug target selection. For example, cell membrane and secreted proteins tend to be more accessible to small molecules and hence more easily targeted than cytosolic or nuclear proteins. Besides, direct target visualization in live cells, or even in whole organisms, can be helpful when analyzing the clinical efficacy of new small molecule drugs. These probes can be used in confocal microscopy and/or flow cytometry to evaluate the effect of the small molecule under study on the protein target. At the present moment, time-resolved optical and fluorescence microscopy are still the best suited techniques to observe processes within living cells, native tissues, and even whole animals. Towards this objective, an important number of organic and inorganic species has been described, including organic dyes, inorganic nanoparticles like quantum dots (QDs) and carbon dots, and fluorescent polymeric nanoparticles. As a detailed review of all these alternatives falls beyond the scope of this work and they have been the focus of excellent recent reviews,^[6] in this section we will highlight those that are more appropriate for probe development and that have been more extensively used in the context of therapeutic target visualization. In this regard, and considering that the size of the reporter group is a critical factor, the field of chemical probes is mainly restricted to small molecule fluorophores due to some fundamental advantages: synthetic accessibility and possibility of tailored structural variations, on-demand wavelength adjustment within a broad spectral range, high brightness, and photostability. Figure 2 shows the main fluorophores used in chemical probes. It is important to note that although there are fluorophores covering all the spectral range between 200 and 800 nm, the longest wavelengths are the most desirable for visualization of biological samples, as they have deeper penetration power and induce less damage to the biological samples. This feature is mandatory if we move towards *in vivo* visualization, where near infrared (NIR) or two photon groups are not only desirable but also required in order to avoid light absorption or tissue damage induction. Although these types of fluorophores are still less common, recent efforts are directed towards their development.^[7]

Figure 2. Most used small molecule one-photon fluorophores. The colour of the fluorophore's shadow indicates its wavelength of maximum emission (λ_{em}).

Labels are also important for high-contrast *in vivo* cell tracking. While fluorescent probes can be used for imaging studies in small animals, magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) contrast agents more useful for larger animals and humans. Common MRI contrast agents are Gd^{3+} -complexes and superparamagnetic iron oxide nanoparticles.^[8] Molecular imaging, often via positron emission tomography (PET), is a noninvasive biomedical technique that facilitates the visualization of drug targets in whole organisms during preclinical studies by monitoring the time-dependent distribution of a compound labeled with positron-emitting isotopes. Accordingly, PET probes allow to study target occupancy and to determine target localization in humans and other preclinical species.^[9] Another important aspect regardless of the imaging technology used, is that live-cell imaging applications generally require probes to be delivered inside cells. For this, careful design of the reporter group and the linker is mandatory so that the probe has an adequate permeability to cross the cellular membrane and reach the organelle of interest.

b) Identification reporter groups: Chemical probes can also be used for target identification. For this application the probe must possess some type of affinity tag, so that the binding group will act as "bait" to capture those proteins (the "preys") for which it has significant affinity. Then, the "bait-prey" complex is pulled down and the captured proteins are identified using mass spectrometry techniques.^[10] The most widely used affinity tags range from the simplest solid supports (sepharose or agarose beads where the binding group is bound by means of an adequate linker) to the extensively applied biotin. In addition, other popular labels include the FLAG peptide as well as a growing number of expression sequences that can be used as affinity tags.^[11]

Finally, it is important to note the bulkiness of some of the visualization or affinity tags. This aspect needs to be taken into account since the introduction of a large tag can be detrimental for target affinity. One strategy to overcome this problem relies on the use of bioorthogonal reactions. This approach entails the introduction of a small group suitable for bioorthogonal reactions in the probe. Due to the abiotic nature and small size of this group, it is conceivable that it will not affect to the target affinity.

Then, once the probe has bound to the protein of interest, the bioorthogonal reaction will be performed and the tag will end up attached to the target protein. Unarguably, the most widespread bioorthogonal reaction is the Cu(I)-catalyzed azide-alkyne cycloaddition (CuAAC) between a terminal alkyne and an azide, although the development of new bioorthogonal reagents is a burgeoning field that is experiencing continuous advances.^[12] Some examples illustrating this methodology will be reviewed in the following sections.

2.3. The linker

When considering the development of a chemical probe from a given ligand, the most important challenge is to avoid losing the properties that have been optimized while evolving such a ligand, including affinity, specificity, solubility, permeability, or localization. The thoughtful choice of the position where the reporter group is introduced and the linker selection can contribute to minimize these problems. Compounds with structurally characterized targets may benefit from the application of computational chemistry and modeling data to assist probe design. In the absence of this information, structure-activity relationship studies must be performed. Regarding the chemical nature of the linker, different considerations such as length and structure (atom composition) must be taken into account. For example, short polyethylene glycol (PEG) linkers are among the most widely used as they can be, in general, incorporated within the synthetic routes in a straightforward manner, their length is easily tunable, and they exhibit good physicochemical properties especially in terms of maintaining an adequate aqueous solubility of the probe. Over the last years, linker chemistry has experienced significant progress,^[13] evolving from the simple structural role of joining two moieties to the development of functionally advanced linkers able to influence aspects such as the localization, delivery and release of the chemical probe.

3. Irreversible probes containing chemoreactive groups

As mentioned before, probes can bind in a reversible or in an irreversible manner. Usually, an irreversible probe keeps the same moieties described in the previous section with the particularity that it incorporates a reactive group, sometimes referred to as warhead. This reactive group can belong to the affinity moiety or can be included by chemical modification of a reversibly binding ligand. Either way, it will be an electrophilic chemical moiety capable of binding nucleophilic residues in the target protein by a chemical reaction. Although there are some additional options in which a reversible probe can be converted into an irreversible one, such as through the use of photoreactive groups (and these will be described in the latter section about irreversible affinity probes), in this section we will focus on irreversible probes that bind their protein targets through polar reactions. Depending on various factors, including the required reactivity and the synthetic feasibility to introduce the reactive functionality into the scaffold, different electrophilic functionalities can be used in order to selectively form a covalent

bond between the probe and a specific nucleophilic amino acid of the target protein. Along this section, a selection of the most representative irreversible probes classified by the protein family targeted will be reviewed.

3.1. G protein-coupled receptors (GPCRs)

GPCRs are one of the largest superfamily of proteins and they represent around one third of the proteins currently targeted by marketed drugs.^[14] They are involved in many physiological processes and represent valuable drug targets. Accordingly, there is a pressing need for the development of new small molecule pharmacological tools that increase our knowledge of existing and novel receptor targets, especially in relation with structural biology, interactome, identification, and localization aspects, fields where there is much information still unknown and where selective covalent probes could be extremely valuable.^[15] However, the development of this class of compounds has proven to be extremely challenging, as suggested by the low number of described covalent probes. Actually, whereas a variety of covalent ligands have been reported for important endogenous systems such as adenosine, adrenergic, cannabinoid, and opioid systems, they have not been evolved towards probes, ie, they are agonists, antagonists, or allosteric ligands that covalently bind their corresponding receptor,^[16] but these molecules lack a reporter moiety that allows their classification as probes. Only very recently a terminal alkyne-bearing human adenosine A2A irreversible probe containing an aryl sulfonyl fluoride electrophilic warhead has been described (Figure 3).^[17]

Figure 3. Structure of LUF7487, a covalent probe for the human adenosine A2A receptor.

3.2. Enzymes

Activity-based probes (ABPs) are compounds that bind in a covalent manner and, thus, irreversibly, to an enzyme. To be considered activity-based binding, the compound must specifically recognize the active site of the protein. Hence, ABPs allow for a direct evaluation of the enzyme activity. ABPs are useful tools for target identification, target engagement, development of high-throughput screenings for the identification of new inhibitors and for the determination of off-target profiles. All these applications entail the screening of compounds for competition against a selective ABP. Also, ABPs can be used for target visualization. In this case, the probe has a fluorescent tag or other subunit suitable for visualization. Usually, ABPs are comprised of a reporter, a short spacer, and a warhead capable of binding in a covalent manner to a structural motif shared among active members of a protein class (Figure 4).

In the last decade, many ABPs able to interact in a functionally dependent manner with almost all known enzyme classes have been developed. Taken into consideration the excellent and comprehensive reviews focused on ABPs available to the readership^[18] in this manuscript we will cover the most recent examples where ABPs provide conceptual advances towards the understanding of specific mechanisms of action and the identification of therapeutic targets. In this regard, important progress has been recently made in the study of specific glycosidases and in the enzymes related with the proteasome and the ubiquitin pathway. In the glycosidase field, the latest research has allowed the development of ABPs against two distinct β -glucuronidase enzymes that are involved in disease, exo-acting β -glucuronidase (GUSB), whose deficiency gives rise to mucopolysaccharidosis type VII, and endo-acting heparanase (HPSE), whose overexpression is implicated in inflammation and cancers. These ABPs, based on the cyclophellitol scaffold (Figure 4A), afford rapid and quantitative visualization of GUSB and HPSE in biological samples, allowing an excellent tool for exploring their activities in normal and disease states.^[19] More recently, the use of ABPs has enabled the identification of Golgi mannosidase II (GMII) inhibitors. Despite the interest of this enzyme in cancer therapeutics and the many structural and mechanistic studies of GMII, no potent and selective inhibitors had been described up to date. The development of manno-epi-cyclophellitol epoxide and aziridines covalent ABPs has enabled, for the first time, the identification of several promising scaffolds for the generation of selective GMII inhibitors. In addition, these ABPs (Figure 4A) have made possible the throughput profiling of α -mannosidases from both human cell lysates and mouse tissue extracts.^[20] As a part of glycoside hydrolase family, α -L-fucosidase catalyzes the hydrolytic removal of L-fucose residues from glycoconjugates. The lack or diminished activity of this enzyme is related to several pathologies, ranging from cystic fibrosis to genetic disorders. To date, antibodies have usually been used for the detection of fucosidases, yet this approach does not give us information about enzyme activity. To overcome this limitation, an affinity probe was recently reported to visualize and locate lysosomal α -L-fucosidase activity in human cells for the first time. A latent trapping unit (*o*-quinone methide derivatives, of which *o*-fluoromethylphenol and *o*-difluoromethylphenol are two important representatives) was added to a recognition unit (pyranoside ring), along with a bodipy reporter tag (Figure 4B). When enzymatic cleavage occurs, a nucleophilic amino acid residue on the enzyme attacks the *in situ* formed methide derivative, which acts as a Michael acceptor, thus irreversibly binding the probe to the enzyme (Figure 4B).^[21] Targeting the ubiquitin (Ub) proteasome system has emerged as a promising therapeutic strategy endowed with potential to address several diseases, and enzymes involved in the ubiquitin addition, such as the E1 ubiquitin-activating enzymes, and those involved in its removal, named deubiquitylating enzymes (DUBs), are attracting a growing interest as drug targets. In particular, last research has been focused on design of ABPs that enable the discovery, detection, and activity determination of E1 enzymes inside intact cells (Figure 4C)^[22] as well as on the development of ABPs specifically designed to address current limitations of the existing tools for DUBs. Among them, the recent availability of cell-permeable DUB ABPs, such as derivative IMP-1710 (Figure 4D), able to work in intact cells and of selective DUB ABPs against the Ub carboxy-terminal hydrolase L1 (UCHL1) stands out.^[23]

Also in the area of the proteasome, the Overkleeft group has developed a number of fluorescent probes to monitor its activity. These ABPs consist of the bodipy fluorophore linked to epoxomicin, a covalent inhibitor of the proteasome (Figure 4E), and they have been used to monitor the proteasome and immunoproteasome activities.^[24]

Figure 4. Structure of representative ABPs and their mechanism of action.

The oxidoreductase superfamily of enzymes has also received attention regarding the development of ABPs. This class includes many mechanistically different enzymes that in general require the use cofactors such as flavins, NADH, or NADPH to be catalytically active. This feature adds an additional difficulty to annotate their function on a gene sequence level, as the encoded amino acids are not characteristic for their catalytic function. Accordingly, the development of specific ABPs for oxidoreductases require a careful study of the chemical transformation being carried out by the enzyme.^[25] Among the most representative examples are the alkynyl-containing ABPs

against P450 monooxygenases where one terminal alkyne is used as the bioorthogonal group to conjugate the desired reporter by click chemistry and the other terminal alkyne acts as the warhead, being converted into a highly electrophilic ketene by the P450 oxidase (Figure 5A).^[26] Similar strategies have enabled the development of ABPs against flavin-dependent monoamine oxidase (MAO) (Figure 5B),^[27] myeloperoxidase^[28] (Figure 5C) or aldehyde dehydrogenases (Figure 5D).^[29]

Figure 5. Structure of representative ABPs for (A) human P450 monooxygenases; (B) monoamine oxidase; (C) myeloperoxidase and (D) aldehyde dehydrogenase.

As described above, up to date, progress in the ABP field has been focused (and limited) to the development of enzyme inhibitors. In a further extension of this already established potential, one of the most recent advances is the use of ABPs for the identification of enzyme activators. This novel approach has enabled the discovery of a first in class activator of LYPLAL1 enzyme (a poorly characterized serine hydrolase with complex genetic links to human metabolic traits) that shows efficacy in a mouse model of diet-induced obesity. Far reaching implications of this work could involve the development of a similar platform for the discovery of activators for other enzyme classes.^[30]

3.3. Other protein classes

Although the development of ABPs has been mostly applied to the enzyme field with some scarce applications to the GPCR area, its remarkable potential to address biology problems has made that the principles of chemoreactivity of nucleophilic amino acids has been extended to other proteins which do not necessarily have catalytic activity. These approaches take advantage of the use of general electrophiles that react with cysteines, such as disulfides or Michael acceptors, including acrylates and vinylsulfones. The main challenge of these applications is that a careful design of the resulting probe is needed to avoid a broad non-specific covalent labeling of all cysteine-containing proteins. More recently, the use of sulfonylfluorides (-SO₂F) and fluorosulfates (-OSO₂F) has broadened the possibilities for amino acid labeling to serine, tyrosine, lysine, or histidine.^[31] Further extension of this strategy has also been applied to the specific functionalization of tyrosines with enhanced nucleophilicity using sulfonyl triazole containing probes^[32] (see Table 1 for a selection of non-mechanistically directed ABPs). The importance of this strategy is that the possibility of developing a covalent probe is not

limited to enzymes but it can be applied to any protein with a binding site provided with a nucleophilic enough residue located in the vicinity.

Table 1. Representative non-mechanistically directed ABPs

Probe	Electrophile	Target amino acid	Ref.
 X = H, OCH ₃ , NO ₂	Michael acceptor (acrylates and vinylsulfones)	Cys	[33]
 SO ₂ F	Sulfonyl fluoride	Tyr	[34]
 Cl	α -Halogenated carbonyl	Cys	[35]
 SO ₂ F	Sulfonyl fluoride	Lys	[31b]
 SO ₂ F	Sulfonyl triazole	Tyr	[32]

The main advantage of chemoreactive probes is that they can be used directly in *in vitro* and *in vivo* experiments without the requirement of any additional activation step. Conversely, their main limitation relies in the fact that they can only be applied in proteins that have a catalytic residue or a nucleophilic enough amino acid strategically located in the proximities of the binding site. For all those proteins that lack any of these features, the use of affinity probes that have been modified with photoreactive moieties is mandatory.

4. Affinity probes

Affinity-based probes (AfBPs) contain the usual parts of any probe (binding and reporter groups, or surrogate bioorthogonal groups that permit the introduction of the reporter group in a later stage after the probe binding to the protein) and a photoreactive moiety that will allow for the covalent crosslinking of the probe to the protein. This strategy permits the conversion of reversible ligands into covalent probes by means of incorporating wisely selected photocrosslinking moieties and reporter groups.

Photoreactive moieties, or photocrosslinkers, are specific subunits that upon photoirradiation generate highly reactive transient chemical species (such as carbenes, nitrenes, or radicals) which covalently cross-link the photoaffinity probe to its binding partner(s) based upon the proximity of both of them. Covalently bound proteins can be then visualized by the reporter group (e.g., fluorophore, biotin, or other suitable label) or isolated for MS-based analysis and identification.

The main advantage of photoreactive moieties over electrophilic crosslinking agents is that they can exist in a “dormant” state and be specifically activated at the desired moment by irradiation, thus, minimizing unspecific crosslinkings. Despite the growing importance of AfBPs, only few photocrosslinkers are currently used in chemical biology, including benzophenone, aryl azide and alkyl or aryl diazirines.^[36] These photoreactive groups, upon their corresponding irradiation wavelength, generate different reactive intermediates. In this regard, benzophenones are converted into an active triplet ketyl biradical upon activation by long wavelengths (350–365 nm), whereas aryl azides form a reactive nitrene by N₂ loss upon irradiation with shorter wavelengths (between 250 and 300 nm). Finally, trifluoromethyl phenyl diazirines and alkyl diazirines generate reactive carbenes via loss of N₂ upon photoirradiation at 350 nm (Figure 6). The selection of the photocrosslinker depends on the context, but in recent years alkyl diazirines have witnessed an increase in popularity because of their intrinsic properties and mechanism of action.^[37] Firstly, because of their small size, steric problems and a potential negative influence on the ligand properties due to their incorporation are reduced. Also, thanks to their crosslinking upon exposure to relatively long wavelength (360 nm) radiation, the damage to target proteins, which can be a worrying factor below 300 nm, is minimum. Another important characteristic of alkyl diazirines is their highly selective and kinetically fast crosslinking derived from their mechanism of action, which involves the generation of an intermediate carbene that exists for picoseconds before reacting with proximal species via C-H or heteroatom-H insertion reducing the risk of nonspecific binding (Figure 6B).

In the last years, the use of AfBPs has experienced a burgeoning development with the increasing coverage of proteins belonging to multiple families. In this section, we will summarize the most representative and recent examples in GPCRs and enzymes, proteins classes where this approach has been mostly used.

4.1. G protein-coupled receptors (GPCRs)

According to their privileged status as drug targets, development of AfBPs has been also applied to the study of GPCRs. Among the different GPCRs, cannabinoid receptors (CBRs) stand out among the most thoroughly analysed by AfBPs, perhaps due to a combination of factors including their undoubted therapeutic importance and the lack of other reliable tools for their study such as antibodies. Specific advances in this field include the clickable and biotinylated AfBPs based on the scaffold of the endogenous cannabinoids anandamide and 2-arachidonoylglycerol^[38] and the biotinylated AfBPs based on the high-affinity ligands HU210 and HU308 that have enabled, for the first time, visualization of CB₁ and CB₂ CBRs in native cells including neurons, microglia, and immune cells (Figure 7A).^[39] Another important photoaffinity probe to profile the targets of the (-)- Δ^9 -tetrahydrocannabinol (Δ^9 -THC), the main natural product with affinity for CBRs, has been recently described. In this case, using Δ^8 -THC as binding group, a diazirine as photoactive group and a terminal alkyne as ligation handle (Figure 7A), the resulting probe kept the affinity for CB₁ and CB₂ CBRs and was used in Neuro2A cells to determine THC interacting proteins.^[40] Also, an area of current interest has been the development of fluorescent probes for the specific detection and quantification of only one of the two CBRs. In this sense, to validate CB₁ as an interesting target or biomarker of immune diseases, the high-affinity cannabinoid ligand HU210 has been coupled to the fluorescent tag Alexa Fluor 488 yielding a high affinity and selective CB₁ fluorescent probe (Figure 7A). This probe was the first tool to directly identify and quantify the expression of CB₁ in human blood and tonsil immune system cells by confocal microscopy and flow cytometry.^[41] Focused on the other cannabinoid receptor, CB₂, a selective probe (LEI121, Figure 7A) based on a CB₂ selective agonist and bearing an alkyne for bioorthogonal introduction of the reporter group and a diazirine as photoreactive moiety, has been recently reported. This probe allows monitoring the endogenous CB₂ expression and engagement in human cells.^[42] Moreover, further extension of this work has led to the description of a set of highly specific azide-bearing fluorescent probes based on the scaffold of the selective CB₂ ligand HU308 (Figure 7) that have been successfully used in a variety of applications and cell types.^[43] Other important GPCRs that have benefited from this type of probes are the serotonergic receptors 5-HT_{1A} and 5-HT₆. The reported AfBPs with selectivity and affinity for these receptors (Figure 7B), have enabled the visualization of physiological vs pathological changes in the protein levels in different cell types as well as the exploration of the target profile of some of their ligands using chemoproteomic approaches.^[44] The development of AfBPs has been extended to allosteric modulators with affinity for the metabotropic glutamate receptor 5 (mGlu5) with the description of the first clickable allosteric photoprobe (Figure 7C).^[45] This type of probes should help to clarify structural and functional aspects of mGlu5 receptor and could be extended to the study of other GPCRs.

Figure 6. (A) Most representative photocrosslinkers and their mechanism. (B) Detailed photoactivation of diazirines.

Figure 7. Representative affinity probes for GPCRs. Affinity probes for (A) cannabinoid receptors; (B) serotonergic 5-HT_{1A} and 5-HT₆ receptors; and (C) metabotropic glutamate 5 receptor.

4.2. Enzymes

One of the most interesting and valuable applications of AfBPs in the field of enzymes is the transformation of known selective enzyme inhibitors provided with some degree of proven therapeutic interest in extremely specific AfBPs that help obtain information about localization, levels of expression, target engagement and off-target identification. In this context, enzyme inhibitors with efficacy as anticancer agents have been one of the compound classes in which this approach has provided extremely valuable information. In this sense, the development of AfBPs of TASIN-1 (truncated APC-selective inhibitor-1) compounds, molecules with important antitumor activity in colorectal cancer, has aided in the identification of their biological targets (Figure 8A), all of them related to the biosynthesis of cholesterol.^[46] Similar strategies involving the synthesis of AfBPs have enabled the discovery of the molecular targets involved in the anticancer effect of ingenol mebutate (Figure 8B), compound approved by the US Food and Drug Administration (FDA) for the treatment of actinic keratosis.^[47] Another important small molecule with antitumor activity is olaparib, a poly-ADP-ribose polymerase (PARP) inhibitor approved for the treatment of ovarian cancer and certain types of breast tumors. Recently disclosed olaparib AfBPs (Figure 8C) allow for the visualization of this enzyme in living cells and the identification of some of its off-targets.^[48] Several histone deacetylase (HDAC) inhibitors have been approved by the FDA

for the treatment of T cell lymphoma and multiple myeloma. Hence, the availability of chemical probes that make possible the visualization of the different HDAC isoforms, the determination of selectivity profiles, and the identification of their protein partners has gained a growing relevance in the field. In this context, a number of AfBPs have been described (Figure 8D), with different selectivity and affinity profiles, which have contributed to clarify variations in the engagement of HDAC isoforms by HDAC inhibitors, to identify changes in the catalytic activity of individual HDAC isoforms and in the interacting partners, and to establish the role of specific HDACs in different diseases such as Friedreich's ataxia.^[49] Extending the use of AfBPs within the field of epigenomics, probes against bromodomain-containing protein 4 (BRD4) have been recently described. These AfBPs are based on GW841819X (a small molecule inhibitor of BRD4) as the binding group and bear a diazirine as the photoactive group and several bioorthogonal groups for the later introduction of the adequate reporter moiety (Figure 8E). These probes have been used for carrying out cell based proteome studies and have succeeded in the identification of APEX1 protein as a relevant off-target of GW841819X.^[50] Similarly, the development of AfBPs has proven to be essential in establishing some of the off-targets of widely prescribed drugs such as the nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs), which main mechanism of action is due to the inhibition of the enzymes cyclooxygenase-1 and -2 (Figure 8F).^[51]

Figure 8. Representative affinity probes for enzymes.

5. Biomedical applications

The ever-growing number of probes and their biological applications has greatly impacted the drug discovery process and how the translation between bench and bedside is made. Chemical probes are nowadays routinely used both in academic and industrial settings for speeding with confidence processes such as target identification and validation and the early identification of unacceptable toxic side effects. In this section, we will revise those areas where the use of chemical probes can provide irreplaceable information and how this knowledge has been exploited in the most advanced translational stages of the drug discovery process.

5.1. Use of probes for discovering unacceptable toxic side effects of (nearly) approved drugs

For most of the approved drugs a comprehensive proteome profile to understand their different interactions is lacking. However, taking into account the recent advances made towards the development of specific probes tailored to different needs, the incorporation of a step aimed at identifying all the off targets of a compound undergoing clinical trials could be relatively easily incorporated to the drug discovery process and save a lot of later grief. The importance of off-targets has revealed with the sad case of thalidomide and, more recently, with the BIA10-2474 clinical trial. As it is well known, during the mid 20th century, thalidomide was prescribed to pregnant women as a treatment for morning sickness. Before its teratogenic activity came to light, several thousand children were born with severe malformations, including limb, ear, cardiac, and gastrointestinal defects. However, it was not until ten years ago when some light was shed on the thalidomide targets responsible for these teratogenic effects. The development of a solid support immobilized probe, based on the thalidomide scaffold (Figure 9A), was crucial in the identification of cereblon (CRBN) as the main culprit of the thalidomide teratogenicity.^[52] This result represents the basis for developing new thalidomide derivatives (which are of current interest as drugs for the treatment of multiple myeloma and other blood cancers) devoid of CRBN affinity and, consequently, of teratogenic effects. More recently, in 2016, the sudden death of one participant in a phase 1 clinical trial of BIA-102474, a new fatty acid amide hydrolase (FAAH) inhibitor developed by the pharmaceutical company Bial, challenged both the field of FAAH inhibitors and the global protocols of clinical trials. FAAH inhibitors have been largely explored in the last two decades for their potential as analgesic and anti-inflammatory drugs. Several FAAH inhibitors have reached clinical phases 1 and 2 and, although a lack of efficacy has precluded their advance to phase 3, no significant toxicities were reported on any of these clinical trials. However, during the first randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled study involving humans of the new FAAH inhibitor BIA10-2474, an unanticipated severe neurologic disorder affected to participants in the final cohort of volunteers receiving the highest dose of the compound.^[53] Potential causes of this unfortunate incident, such as errors in the manufacturing or handling of the compound or in the conduct of the trial, were dismissed by the corresponding authorities. Similarly, FAAH inhibition was also discarded as the source of the toxicity, considering that other structurally unrelated FAAH inhibitors have exhibited good safety profiles in phase 1 and 2 clinical trials. Hence, the underlying mechanism of the toxic cerebral syndrome caused by BIA10-2474 remained

unknown until the application of activity-based proteomic methods to establish the protein interaction landscape of BIA10-2474 in human cells and tissues. This analysis revealed that the compound inhibited several lipases that are not targeted by other previously developed FAAH inhibitors that have reached clinical trials. BIA10-2474, unlike other FAAH inhibitors, produced substantial alterations in lipid networks in human cortical neurons, suggesting that promiscuous lipase inhibitors have the potential to cause metabolic deregulation in the nervous system.^[54] Soon after, the investigation was extended to the most important metabolites formed in the body after BIA10-2474 administration. After structural characterization, these metabolites and BIA10-2474 were converted into clickable probes (see Figure 9B for the BIA10-2474 based ABP) and used for comprehensive proteomic studies, which allowed to identify all of their targets and to suggest the off-target inhibition of aldehyde dehydrogenase ALDH2 as a potential mediator in the neurotoxic effects of BIA10-2474.^[55]

Overall, these studies highlight the general utility of ABPs as versatile chemical tools to assess on-target engagement and off-target activity of covalent drugs to guide therapeutic development.

Figure 9. Selected probes successfully used for the identification of protein targets involved in toxic side effects.

5.2. Use of probes for polypharmacology analysis and drug repurposing

It is a fact that the mechanism of action of approved drugs is not always totally understood. In this regard, the use of chemical probes can make an important contribution towards this objective. As described in the preceding section, off-targets can be responsible of dramatic toxicities. However, they can also represent valuable opportunity to increase efficacy if correctly managed. In this regard, small molecules with simultaneous affinity by multiple proteins have improved clinical benefits in certain heterogeneous diseases, such as cancer or neuronal disorders.^[56] Alternatively, the identification of off-targets can reveal a different application for the drug, providing a firm

scientific basis for drug repurposing, a strategy that has succeeded in the identification of new drugs for unmet clinical needs^[57] and which has proven of undeniable value in times of urgent needs, as we have recently witnessed with the COVID-19 pandemic.^[58] Both objectives, drug repurposing and off-target identification share a common need: the availability of compounds able to capture, visualize, and identify all the targets of a given drug. In this regard, and as detailed in the former sections, both ABPs and AfBPs have contributed to profile the targets of marketed NSAIDs,^[51] or anticancer compounds such as olaparib^[48] or ingenol mebutate.^[47]

5.3. Use of probes for finding the molecular target of natural products with therapeutic activities

Target identification of natural products remains an area of high relevance. Natural products coming mainly from plants and microorganisms provide an underexplored rich source of new drugs. Many plants are known to produce therapeutic effects, and accordingly they could represent the starting point for the development of new medicines. However, two aspects need to be addressed before any systematic study can be addressed: the identification of the active principle and the identification of the molecular target(s).

Usually, after having established the active compound, the second step, ie, the delineation of its mechanism of action, is attempted with the development of probes. In this case, the natural product can act as the binding group, and a reporter group, together with a warhead or a photoreactive moiety, are added to the structure. In this manner, the proteins targeted by the compound can be visualized or isolated and identified using proteomics. After that, exhaustive biological studies are carried out to confirm the importance of the identified target(s) in the intended application using cellular and animal disease models, and if all these steps are successful we would be ready to start the drug discovery process with an identified molecular target and an active compound for treating a specific disease.

Although some reviews have revised different examples where this approach has been applied and are available to the interested reader,^[11] in this section we will highlight some of the most recent advances carried out in this field. For example, the natural product gambogic acid (GBA), a polyprenylated xanthone derived from the resin of *Garcinia hanburyi* trees, is a promising anticancer agent for the treatment of non-small-cell lung, colon, and renal cancers. A biotinylated analog of GBA (Figure 10A) has identified the heat shock protein Hsp90 as the main target involved in its antitumor activity.^[59] These studies suggest that GBA represents a valuable lead for driving new drug discovery efforts exploiting Hsp90 inhibition. Another important application of natural products is their potential for the discovery of new antibiotics. In this regard, an elegant approach has used a benzophenone containing natural product, elegaphenone, as the starting point to obtain an alkynylated probe (Figure 10B). This probe has enabled to uncover intriguing biological interactions with the transcriptional regulator AlgP in *P. aeruginosa*.^[60] Another set of interesting natural products belong to the class of flavonoids, as they are among the most studied bioactive plant polyphenols but with a limited knowledge about their binding targets. Aiming at shedding some light on this aspect, a series of probes to investigate flavonoid-protein specific interactions (Figure 10C) have been reported.^[61]

Figure 10. Selected probes used for finding the molecular target of natural products with therapeutic activities.

6. Outlook and future perspectives

The development of new synthetic tools and chemical biology strategies has largely prompted the discovery of a growing number of chemical probes that allow addressing problems that were considered irresolvable just few years ago. In this review we have described the most recent additions and advances undergone by the field with a special focus on the progress made during the last decade. Nonetheless, important challenges still lie ahead including the development of ABPs for underexplored enzyme families or for the profiling of alternative binding sites such as the allosteric ones. Also, the study of membrane proteins should benefit from the availability of chemical probes specifically adapted to their particular features. In this regard, careful consideration of their hydrophobicity, conformation and particular amino acid accessibility should guide the design and synthesis of optimized probes able to profile membrane proteins. This is an area of particular interest taking into account that more than 50% of approved drugs target a membrane protein (either GPCR, ion channel or receptor with kinase function), however, their interrogation regarding their levels, aggregation or activity state is particularly challenging still today.

Considering the dynamism of the area and its endeavoring objectives, there is no doubt that the chemistry behind the development of new probes will continue its evolution making fundamental contributions to the deep understanding of the biology that governs the outcome of pharmacological strategies.

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Chemical biology for drug discovery. The earliest preclinical stages of drug discovery must generate information about the identity, the *in vivo* engagement, and the endogenous levels of the targeted protein(s). In this review, we outline the main strategies by which chemical probes, compounds that rely on chemical reactions to give an answer to specific biological questions, are contributing to currently challenging biomedical applications.